

The CERN@school Programme: MoEDAL bibliography

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Abstract. This document presents a bibliography of publications relating directly or indirectly to the Monopole and Exotics Detector at the LHC (MoEDAL). It is intended to serve as a reference for members of the MoEDAL Collaboration, students involved in research activities connected to MoEDAL, and indeed anyone with an interest in the latest searches for Dirac’s hypothesised magnetic monopole at CERN’s Large Hadron Collider. Both quick reference summary tables, indexed by BibTeX citation code (as used in the accompanying BibTeX file), and a full bibliography in the BibTeX `unsrt` style are provided. Suggestions, comments, or additions from all communities are welcome; please contact the corresponding author for more information.

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1. Introduction

1.1. *The MoEDAL experiment*

The Monopole and Exotics Detector at the LHC [1] is the latest addition to a long line of experiments that have searched for Dirac’s hypothesised magnetic monopole. Based at the Large Hadron Collider’s Interaction Point 8 (IP8), it is housed in the same experimental cavern as the LHCb experiment. The three major subdetectors – the Nuclear Track Detectors (NTDs), Magnetic Monopole Trapping (MMT) detectors, and Timepix detector array – are largely situated in and around the LHCb VeLo (Vertex Locator) housing. It is hoped that these subdetectors will provide experimental evidence for the production of magnetic monopoles or other highly-ionising Beyond Standard Model (BSM) physics produced in the LHC’s highest energy laboratory-based proton-proton, proton-lead, or lead-lead collisions as – to date – no such evidence has been reported in any of publications featured here.

1.2. *The scope of this document*

This document aims to provide a bibliography for all those with an interest in the work of the MoEDAL Collaboration – be they collaboration members, students associated with MoEDAL-related research, or members of the public – to aid with background reading, literature searches, and preparing publications. It should cover publications relating to the theory behind and experimental searches for magnetic monopoles and other highly-ionising phenomena that are within reach of the MoEDAL experiment’s detector systems.

While such a document can never be fully comprehensive, the author(s) will endeavour to make it as complete as possible. Additions, comments and suggestions can and should be submitted to the document’s GitHub repository[†].

1.3. *Using this bibliography*

The bibliography is presented in the standard BibTeX `unsrt` style in the final section of this document. However, the BibTeX source file may be found in this document’s GitHub repository and its contents re-used as necessary.

1.4. *Overview*

After this introduction (Section 1), quick reference summary tables of the publications (with BibTeX citation codes and brief notes) are provided in Section 2. The full bibliography follows.

[†] <https://github.com/CERNatschool/moedal-bibliography>

2. Summary tables

The following tables contain the LaTeX citation code, Digital Object Identifier (DOI) – or URL where no DOI is available – brief notes, year of publication, and number in the actual bibliography at the end of this document, for each publication. Publications of particular importance are denoted with an asterisk in the notes column.

Table 1: MoEDAL-related publications (1/8).

Citation	DOI or URL	Notes	Year	Ref.
Maxwell1865	10.1098/rstl.1865.0008	Maxwell's equations.	1865	[2]
Curie1894	10.1051/jphysrap:018940030041501	First mention of magnetic charge.	1894	[3]
Dirac1928	10.1098/rspa.1928.0023	" <i>The Quantum Theory of the Electron</i> ".	1928	[4]
Dirac1930	10.1098/rspa.1930.0013	" <i>A Theory of Electrons and Protons</i> ".	1930	[5]
Dirac1931	10.1098/rspa.1931.0130	Dirac's magnetic monopole prediction. *	1931	[6]
Dirac1948	10.1103/PhysRev.74.817	" <i>The Theory of Magnetic Poles</i> ".	1948	[7]
Malkus1951	10.1103/PhysRev.83.899	Monopole/matter interactions.	1951	[8]
Birks1952	10.1103/PhysRev.86.569	Monopole/scintillator interactions.	1952	[9]
Goto1958	10.1143/JPSJ.13.1413	Proposes method for magnetic material searches.	1958	[10]
Goto1963	10.1103/PhysRev.132.387	Meteorite/emulsion search.	1963	[11]
Petukhov1963	10.1016/0029-5582(63)90076-2	Vaporising a meteorite!	1963	[12]
Carithers1966	10.1103/PhysRev.149.1070	Solenoid-based cosmic monopole search.	1966	[13]
Schwinger1966	10.1103/PhysRev.144.1087	" <i>Magnetic charge and quantum field theory</i> ".	1966	[14]
Alvager1967	10.1016/0370-2693(67)90367-X	Search for massive, charged particles in deuterium.	1967	[15]
Zwanziger1968	10.1103/PhysRev.176.1480	A theory paper on dyons.	1968	[16]
Fleischer1969a	10.1103/PhysRev.177.2029	Manganese nodules (ocean floor)/Lexan NTD search.	1969	[17]
Fleischer1969b	10.1103/PhysRev.184.1393	Another manganese nodule-based search.	1969	[18]
Schwinger1969	10.1126/science.165.3895.757	" <i>A Magnetic Model of Matter</i> ".	1969	[19]
Parker1970	10.1086/150442	Lecture – the Parker bound.*	1970	[20]
Eberhard1971	10.1103/PhysRevD.4.3260	Monopoles in moon rocks!	1971	[21]
Kolm1971	10.1103/PhysRevD.4.1285	A deep-sea sediment search.	1971	[22]
Carrigan1973	10.1103/PhysRevD.8.3717	300 GeV proton search at NAL (pre-1974 Fermilab).	1973	[23]
Ross1973	10.1103/PhysRevD.8.698	More moon rocks.	1973	[24]
Georgi1974	10.1103/PhysRevLett.32.438	" <i>Unity of All Elementary Particle Forces</i> ".	1974	[25]

Table 2: MoEDAL-related publications (2/8).

Citation	DOI or URL	Notes	Year	Ref.
Polyakov1974	https://inspirehep.net/record/90679	Polyakov's GUT monopole paper.*	1974	[26]
tHooft1974	10.1016/0550-3213(74)90486-6	't Hooft's GUT monopole paper.*	1974	[27]
Schwinger1975	10.1103/PhysRevD.12.3105	Schwinger on dyons.	1975	[28]
Price1975	10.1103/PhysRevLett.35.487	Balloon-borne NTDs with a "monopole" signal!	1975	[29]
Friedlander1975	10.1103/PhysRevLett.35.1103	That's no monopole...	1975	[30]
Carrigan1976	10.1103/PhysRevD.13.1823	Looking for monopoles in ocean water and the atmosphere.	1976	[31]
Holt1976	10.1103/PhysRevLett.36.183	Search in Radon (not necessarily monopoles).	1976	[32]
Troost1976	https://inspirehep.net/record/109302	"Monopoles from Dipoles" – theory.	1976	[33]
Kittel1977	10.1103/PhysRevB.15.333	Monopole/ferromagnetic material interactions (theory).	1977	[34]
Muller1977	10.1126/science.196.4289.521	Search for odd hydrogen using an 88-inch cyclotron.	1977	[35]
Ahlen1978	10.1103/PhysRevD.17.229	"Stopping-power formula for magnetic monopoles".	1978	[36]
Middleton1979	10.1103/PhysRevLett.43.429	Using a tandem accelerator as a spectrometer – oxygen.	1979	[37]
Smith1979	10.1016/0550-3213(79)90006-3	Heavy stable particle search in heavy water at RAL.	1979	[38]
Ahlen1980	10.1103/RevModPhys.52.121	HIP energy loss.	1980	[39]
Carrigan1980	10.1038/288348a0	Limits on GUT monopoles from properties of the Earth.	1980	[40]
tHooft1980	http://inspirehep.net/record/144074	Summer seminar.	1980	[41]
Bartlett1981	10.1103/PhysRevD.24.612	Fermilab bubble chamber magnet/Lexan search.	1981	[42]
Goddard1981	10.1016/0550-3213(81)90311-4	Magnetic charge in Higgs theories.	1981	[43]
Kirkman1981	10.1103/PhysRevD.24.999	"Asymptotic Analysis of the Monopole Structure".	1981	[44]
Cabrera1982	10.1103/PhysRevLett.48.1378	Candidate event in a superconducting loop at Stanford.	1982	[45]
Ahlen1982	10.1103/PhysRevD.26.2347	Low β monopole stopping power calculations.	1982	[46]
Carrigan1982	10.1038/scientificamerican0482-106	"Superheavy Magnetic Monopoles".	1982	[47]
Longo1982	10.1103/PhysRevD.25.2399	Indirect and direct limits on massive monopoles.	1982	[48]
Smith1982	10.1016/0550-3213(82)90271-1	Heavy water search with a ToF spectrometer.	1982	[49]

Table 3: MoEDAL-related publications (3/8).

Citation	DOI or URL	Notes	Year	Ref.
Rizzo1982	10.1103/PhysRevD.25.235	"Grand Unification and Parity Restoration at Low-energies".	1982	[50]
Olaussen1983	10.1016/0550-3213(83)90560-6	Monopole-fermion binding energy calculations.	1983	[51]
Carrigan1983	10.1038/305673a0	Review article in Nature.	1983	[52]
Ebisu1983	10.1143/JPSJ.52.2617	Ferric sand search with a SQUID.	1983	[53]
Bracci1984	10.1016/0550-3213(84)90566-2	More monopole binding energy calculations.	1984	[54]
Olaussen1984	10.1103/PhysRevLett.52.325	Proton capture by monopoles (calculations).	1984	[55]
Dick1984	10.1103/PhysRevLett.53.431	Search for anomalous sodium isotopes with photon bursts.	1984	[56]
Preskill1984	10.1146/annurev.ns.34.120184.002333	Preskill's review.*	1984	[57]
Turkevich1984	10.1103/PhysRevD.30.1876	Massive particle search with processed graphite.	1984	[58]
Weinberg1984	10.1016/0550-3213(84)90526-1	"Magnetic monopoles with $Z(n)$ charges".	1984	[59]
Ebisu1985	10.1088/0305-4616/11/8/005	Iron ore-based search.	1985	[60]
Farhi1985	10.1103/PhysRevD.32.2452	Heavy ion-based search for strange matter (proposal).	1985	[61]
Haber1985	10.1016/0370-1573(85)90051-1	Haber and Kane's classic supersymmetry review paper.*	1985	[62]
Caplin1986	10.1038/321402a0	Caplin's unexplained monopole event.*	1986	[63]
Dick1986	10.1103/PhysRevD.33.32	Superheavy sodium search (cont.).	1986	[64]
Groom1986	10.1016/0370-1573(86)90037-2	Monopole search review.	1986	[65]
Jones1986	10.1038/321127a0	"Muon-catalysed fusion revisited".	1986	[66]
Kovalik1986	10.1103/PhysRevA.33.1183	SQUID search using deeply-buried rocks.	1986	[67]
Ebisu1987	10.1103/PhysRevD.36.3359	Iron ore/SQUID search.	1987	[68]
Hodges1987	10.1103/PhysRevD.35.2024	"Parker limit for monopoles with large magnetic charge".	1987	[69]
Norman1987	10.1103/PhysRevLett.58.1403	Super-massive particle search in Fe (γ and β).	1987	[70]
Price1987	10.1103/PhysRevLett.59.2523	Proton-antiproton (CoM 1800 GeV) NTD search at Fermilab.	1987	[71]
TASSO1988	10.1007/BF01624358	Monopole/dyon search in e^+e^- with TASSO at DESY.	1988	[72]
Brugger1989	10.1038/337434a0	"Search for strange matter by Rutherford backscattering".	1989	[73]

Table 4: MoEDAL-related publications (4/8).

Citation	DOI or URL	Notes	Year	Ref.
Norman1989	10.1103/PhysRevD.39.2499	Super-massive particle search in Lead (beta/gamma).	1989	[74]
Bermon1990	10.1103/PhysRevLett.64.839	Superconducting induction search at BNL.	1990	[75]
Bertani1990	10.1209/0295-5075/12/7/007	1.8TeV Tevatron search with NTDs at E0.	1990	[76]
Hemmi1990	10.1103/PhysRevD.41.2074	Low Z anomalous isotope searches with a tandem accelerator.	1990	[77]
Price1990	10.1103/PhysRevLett.65.149	NTD search at Tevatron's D0 experiment (1.8 TeV).	1990	[78]
Boyd1991	10.1016/0920-5632(91)90324-8	A search for stable strangelets in Helium.	1991	[79]
Gardner1991	10.1103/PhysRevD.44.622	Another SQUID-based cosmic monopole search.	1991	[80]
Huber1991	10.1103/PhysRevD.44.636	SQUID-based search for cosmic ray monopoles.	1991	[81]
Pinfold1991	10.1016/0168-9002(91)90356-U	Monopole detector descriptions at LEP's OPAL experiment.	1991	[82]
Polikanov1991	10.1007/BF01288200	Updated Uranium backscattering search.	1991	[83]
Kinoshita1992	10.1103/PhysRevD.46.R881	NTD search at LEP, a.k.a. MODAL.	1992	[84]
Verkerk1992	10.1103/PhysRevLett.68.1116	"Search for Superheavy Hydrogen in Sea Water".	1992	[85]
Pinfold1993	10.1016/0370-2693(93)90346-J	HIP search at LEP's OPAL experiment.*	1993	[86]
Yamagata1993	10.1103/PhysRevD.47.1231	A search for heavy hydrogen in deep sea water.	1993	[87]
Jeon1995	10.1103/PhysRevLett.75.1443	1995 search for trapped monopoles with a SQUID.	1995	[88]
Vandegriff1996	10.1016/0370-2693(95)01443-8	Searching for strange quark matter in helium.	1996	[89]
Cho1997	10.1016/S0370-2693(96)01492-X	The Cho-Mason electroweak monopole.*	1997	[90]
Ambrosio1997	10.1016/S0370-2693(97)00684-9	MACRO results (1989-1995).	1997	[91]
Derkaoui1998	10.1016/S0927-6505(98)00016-4	Monopole/dyon energy losses in the Earth (calculations).	1998	[92]
D01998	10.1103/PhysRevLett.81.524	Diphoton search for monopoles at the D0 experiment.	1998	[93]
Kusenko1998	10.1016/S0370-2693(97)01375-0	"Supersymmetric Q-balls as dark matter".	1998	[94]
Perillo1998	10.1103/PhysRevLett.81.2416	Trapped strange matter search using heavy ion activation.	1998	[95]
Dienes1999	10.1016/S0550-3213(98)00669-5	GUTs and extra dimensions.	1999	[96]
Lyth1999	10.1016/S0370-1573(98)00128-8	Particle physics and inflation (cosmology).	1999	[97]

Table 5: MoEDAL-related publications (5/8).

Citation	DOI or URL	Notes	Year	Ref.
Trodden1999	10.1103/RevModPhys.71.1463	Review of electroweak baryogenesis.	1999	[98]
Gamberg2000	10.1023/A:1003668812097	Low-mass monopole limits in the Tevatron context.	2000	[99]
Bertram2000	inspirehep.net/record/526421	Confidence limits - a recipe.*	2000	[100]
Kalbfleisch2000	10.1103/PhysRevLett.85.5292	Beam pipe search at D0 (post-Tevatron).	2000	[101]
Perl2001	10.1142/S0217751X01003548	Review of searches for massive, stable particles.	2001	[102]
Javorsek2001a	10.1103/PhysRevD.64.012005	Australian mass spectrometer search in gold.	2001	[103]
Javorsek2001b	10.1103/PhysRevLett.87.231804	Search in Au/Fe from RHIC, NASA satellite, etc. samples.	2001	[104]
Javorsek2002	10.1103/PhysRevD.65.072003	More Au/Fe mass spectrometer searches in Australia.	2002	[105]
Ambrosio2002	10.1016/S0168-9002(01)02169-6	The MACRO detector.	2002	[106]
MACRO2002	10.1140/epjc/s2002-01046-9	Final results from the MACRO experiment.*	2002	[107]
Medipix2002	10.1109/TNS.2002.803788	The Medipix2 detector.	2002	[108]
Feng2003	10.1103/PhysRevD.68.085018	"Graviton cosmology in universal extra dimensions".	2003	[109]
Hestenes2003a	10.1119/1.1522700	Geometric Algebra (c.f. all Maxwell's equations in one).	2003	[110]
Hestenes2003b	10.1119/1.1571836	Spacetime physics with Geometric Algebra.	2003	[111]
Kalbfleisch2004	10.1103/PhysRevD.69.052002	Monopole limits from D0/CDF beampipe and detector bits.	2004	[112]
Mueller2004	10.1103/PhysRevLett.92.022501	Atmospheric heavy helium isotope search.	2004	[113]
Polchinski2004	10.1142/S0217751X0401866X	"Monopoles, duality, and string theory".	2004	[114]
Bertone2005	10.1016/j.physrep.2004.08.031	Particle dark matter - review.	2005	[115]
H12005	10.1140/epjc/s2005-02201-6	H1 beam pipe search for monopoles at HERA (300 GeV)/	2005	[116]
Lu2005	10.1016/j.nuclphysa.2005.01.038	Atmospheric laser spectroscopy search for strangelets.	2005	[117]
CDF2006	10.1103/PhysRevLett.96.201801	Direct monopole searches at Tevatron's CDF (1.96 TeV).	2006	[118]
Geant42006	10.1109/TNS.2006.869826	GEANT4 - developments and applications.	2006	[119]
Milton2006	10.1088/0034-4885/69/6/R02	Post-Tevatron monopole search review.	2006	[120]
Sjostrand2006	10.1088/1126-6708/2006/05/026	PYTHIA 6.4 Physics and Manual.	2006	[121]

Table 6: MoEDAL-related publications (6/8).

Citation	DOI or URL	Notes	Year	Ref.
Fairbairn2007	10.1016/j.physrep.2006.10.002	Review of massive, stable particle searches at colliders.	2007	[122]
Hooper2007	10.1016/j.physrep.2007.09.003	Universal Extra Dimensions at colliders.	2007	[123]
Koch2007	10.1088/0954-3899/34/8/S44	Black holes at the LHC? Probably not (yet).	2007	[124]
Timepix2007	10.1016/j.nima.2007.08.079	The original Timepix paper.*	2007	[125]
Timepix2007Erratum	10.1016/j.nima.2007.11.003	Erratum for the original Timepix paper.*	2008	[126]
Lintott2008	10.1111/j.1365-2966.2008.13689.x	Galaxy Zoo!	2008	[127]
BAIKAL2008	10.1016/j.astropartphys.2008.03.006	Search at the Baikal Neutrino Telescope.	2008	[128]
LHCb2008	10.1088/1748-0221/3/08/S08005	The LHCb detector.	2008	[129]
OPAL2008	10.1016/j.physletb.2008.03.057	Monopole search with OPAL at LEP2.	2008	[130]
SLIM2008a	10.1140/epjc/s10052-008-0597-3	High-altitude monopole search with SLIM.	2008	[131]
SLIM2008b	10.1140/epjc/s10052-008-0747-7	High-altitude strange quark matter/Q-ball search with SLIM.	2008	[132]
RICE2008	10.1103/PhysRevD.78.075031	Antarctic search with the Radio Ice Cherenkov Experiment.	2008	[133]
Sjostrand2008	10.1016/j.cpc.2008.01.036	PYTHIA 8.1 - an introduction.	2008	[134]
Pinfold2009	10.1016/j.radmeas.2009.10.062	Review of NTD searches.*	2009	[135]
AMANDA2010	10.1140/epjc/s10052-010-1411-6	Antarctic monopole search with AMANDA-II.	2010	[136]
Alwall2011	10.1007/JHEP06(2011)128	MADGRAPH 5.	2011	[137]
ANITA2011	10.1103/PhysRevD.83.023513	ANITA-II - antarctic balloon-borne monopole search.	2011	[138]
ATLAS2011a	10.1016/j.physletb.2011.03.033	ATLAS HIP search at 7 TeV.	2011	[139]
ATLAS2011b	10.1016/j.physletb.2011.08.042	Long-lived particle search with ATLAS (7 TeV).	2011	[140]
ATLAS2011c	10.1016/j.physletb.2011.05.010	ATLAS search for stable hadronising squarks etc. (7 TeV).	2011	[141]
Burdin2011	10.1016/j.nima.2011.10.044	HIPs in Argon detectors.	2012	[142]
Simpson2012	10.1111/j.1365-2966.2012.20770.x	The Milky Way Project: first data release.	2012	[143]
Kendrew2012	10.1088/0004-637X/755/1/71	The Milky Way Project: Infrared bubble stuff.	2012	[144]
ANTARES2012	10.1016/j.astropartphys.2012.02.007	Monopole search with ANTARES (Mediterranean ν exp.).	2012	[145]

Table 7: MoEDAL-related publications (7/8).

Citation	DOI or URL	Notes	Year	Ref.
ATLAS2012a	10.1103/PhysRevLett.109.261803	ATLAS monopole search (7 TeV).	2012	[146]
ATLAS2012b	10.1103/PhysRevLett.108.251801	ATLAS Higgs to long-lived particle search (7 TeV).	2012	[147]
ATLAS2012c	10.1016/j.physletb.2012.08.020	The ATLAS Higgs discovery paper.	2012	[148]
CMS2012a	10.1016/j.physletb.2012.08.021	The CMS Higgs discovery paper.	2012	[149]
DeRoeck2012a	10.1140/epjc/s10052-012-1985-2	Finding HIPs at the LHC.	2012	[150]
DeRoeck2012b	10.1140/epjc/s10052-012-2212-x	MMT development with CMS beam pipe fragments.	2012	[151]
Epele2012	10.1140/epjp/i2012-12060-8	Proposed monopole/monopolium diphoton LHC searches.	2012	[152]
Rajantie2012	10.1080/00107514.2012.685693	Introduction to magnetic monopoles.*	2012	[153]
PDG2012	10.1103/PhysRevD.86.010001	PDG's Review of Particle Physics.	2012	[154]
ATLAS2013a	10.1016/j.physletb.2013.04.036	Long-lived, multi-charged particle search at ATLAS (7 TeV).	2013	[155]
ATLAS2013b	10.1016/j.physletb.2013.02.015	Slepton/R-hadron search at ATLAS (7 TeV).	2013	[156]
ATLAS2013c	10.1016/j.physletb.2013.02.058	Displaced muonic lepton jets at ATLAS (7 TeV).	2013	[157]
ATLAS2013d	10.1016/j.physletb.2013.01.042	Displaced muon+jets vertex search at ATLAS (7 TeV).	2013	[158]
ATLAS2013e	10.1016/j.physletb.2013.08.010	Higgs production, couplings in diboson final states at ATLAS (7 TeV).	2013	[159]
Ba112013	10.1016/j.nuclphysb.2012.10.003	" <i>Parton distributions with LHC data</i> ".	2013	[160]
Bendtz2013	10.1103/PhysRevLett.110.121803	Polar volcanic rock search with a SQUID (ft. P. Mermod!).	2013	[161]
CMS2013a	10.1007/JHEP07(2013)122	Search for long-lived charged particles at CMS (7/8TeV).	2013	[162]
CMS2013b	10.1007/JHEP02(2013)085	CMS long-lived neutral particle search (leptonic).	2013	[163]
CMS2013c	https://cds.cern.ch/record/1563591	CMS Physics Analysis Summary - displaced dijet search.	2013	[164]
Farina2013	10.1007/JHEP08(2013)022	Modifying "naturalness" - and testing it.	2013	[165]
Mermod2013	http://arxiv.org/abs/1305.3718	Mermod on monopoles at Moriond 2013.	2013	[166]
TLEP2013a	http://arxiv.org/abs/1305.6498	TLEP (Higgs factory) proposal.	2013	[167]
PDG2014	10.1088/1674-1137/38/9/090001	PDG's Review of Particle Physics.	2014	[168]
Beaumont2014	10.1088/0067-0049/214/1/3	The Milky Way Project - Citizen Science and Machine Learning.	2014	[169]

Table 8: MoEDAL-related publications (8/8).

Citation	DOI or URL	Notes	Year	Ref.
TLEP2013b	10.1007/JHEP01(2014)164	The TLEP physics case.	2014	[170]
MoEDAL2014	10.1142/S0217751X14300506	The MoEDAL physics programme.*	2014	[171]
ATLAS2015a	10.1103/PhysRevD.93.052009	ATLAS HIP etc. search (8 TeV).	2015	[172]
Burdin2015	10.1016/j.physrep.2015.03.004	"Non-collider searches for stable massive particles".	2015	[173]
Cho2015	10.1140/epjc/s10052-015-3290-3	"Finite energy electroweak dyon".	2015	[174]
IceCube2015	10.1140/epjc/s10052-016-3953-8	Monopole searches with IceCube.	2015	[175]
Patrizzii2015	10.1146/annurev-nucl-102014-022137	Latest status of magnetic monopole searches.*	2015	[176]
Kimm2016	10.1140/epjc/s10052-015-3290-3	"Mass of the electroweak monopole".	2016	[177]
Ellis2016	10.1016/j.physletb.2016.02.048	Finding electroweak monopoles at the LHC.	2016	[178]
Patrizzii2016	MoEDAL-Note-2016-001	Monopole energy loss in Al, Fe, and Cu (analysis note).	2016	[179]
MoEDAL2016a	10.1007/JHEP08(2016)067	MoEDAL's MMT results (8 TeV).	2016	[180]

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Version History

Table 9: Version history.

Version	Description	Author
1.0	Initial version.	TW